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Direct Insertion of Turbulent Windfields via Characteristic Boundary Method in a Blade-Resolved DDES CFD Code

Louis Gagnon, Carsten Müller and Thorsten Lutz

University of Stuttgart, Institute of Aerodynamics and Gas Dynamics, Germany

E-mail: gagnon@iag.uni-stuttgart.de

Abstract. This paper presents the implementation of a boundary condition (BC) for the direct insertion of time- and space-resolved (3D) turbulent wind fields into a Delayed Detached Eddy Simulation (DDES) Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) code. The method leverages the characteristic variable BC framework to enforce velocities at domain boundaries while maintaining numerical stability by preventing spurious reflections. The implementation was validated using a constrained Mann turbulence box matched to complex terrain meteorological mast measurements on computational grids with different topologies and geometries. Results of the two-point space-time correlation, the mean velocity and turbulence profiles showed that flow fields are accurately inserted, with streamwise velocity correlations near unity at the inlet and coherent structures preserved beyond 100 m downstream. Pressure fluctuations remained low throughout the domain, confirming the absence of undesired reflections from the BC. Additionally, a precursor-successor approach confirmed the ability to separate terrain-scale and turbine-scale simulations, and a stress test confirmed that the simulation remains numerically stable under extreme wind conditions.

1. Introduction

Accurate prediction of fatigue loads is critical for wind turbine design and certification. Although Blade Element Momentum (BEM) methods are the industry standard for aeroelastic calculations, the European Union (EU) project AVATAR (AdVanced Aerodynamic Tools for lARge Rotors) demonstrated that BEM-based fatigue load predictions can differ by approximately 15% compared to higher-fidelity methods [1]. Since coherent structures in the turbine inflow directly influence power output fluctuations, blade loading, and wake development [2], blade-resolved CFD with realistic, structure-preserving turbulent inflow is needed to accurately assess structural response and performance.

Various methods exist to generate turbulent flow fields and inject them into a CFD domain [3, 4]. To improve on accuracy or computational efficiency, a novel BC was implemented into the FLOWer [5] CFD code: it enforces a time-varying 3D cell-resolved velocity field from a source such as a precursor simulation or a synthetic turbulence box. The present work focuses on the accurate insertion of turbulence in the near-blade and near-turbine environment rather than on atmospheric modeling at larger scales.

This new development reduces reflections of flow field disturbances, maintaining numerical stability with complex terrain inflow. It also eliminates the need for buffer zones between the

inlet and a turbulence forcing region for the non-thermal conditions considered here, thereby enabling smaller computational domains and greater flexibility in specifying wind directions and generating meshes. The new BC, referred to herein as the Gust BC, was programmed to allow its simultaneous use on all boundaries of the CFD domain. As the current focus is on turbulence and its coherent structures, the Gust BC currently only inserts the velocity terms. Thermal effects and atmospheric stratification are not considered but are planned for future implementation; over small domains with moderate wind velocities and inflows characterized by hill and forest wakes, mechanical mixing is expected to dominate over buoyancy effects within the Prandtl layer.

This paper presents details of the implementation of the Gust BC and assesses its accuracy and stability when inserting turbulence associated with wind fields in complex terrain into the CFD domain, as well as the code's capability to transport the inserted turbulence and remain numerically stable under intense wind conditions. The computational grids, turbulent inflow fields, and a selection of flow field outputs are made available in a public repository¹.

2. Background and Implementation

Since in the authors' research group an approach based on variants of the Mann box [6] is used to generate the flow fields and the focus of this paper is on direct insertion of the flow variables at a boundary condition using the ghost cells method, other methods are not discussed herein. Careful boundary condition treatment is critical for stability and convergence in compressible flow simulations. Simple extrapolation methods can generate spurious reflections that contaminate the solution, particularly for time-varying inflow conditions or when flow structures interact with domain boundaries. Characteristic boundary conditions address this by decomposing the flow into characteristic waves and controlling information propagation at boundaries based on wave directions. Although this approach has long been known and used, recent developments in implementing characteristic boundary conditions for compressible Navier-Stokes CFD codes using ghost cells continue to demonstrate their importance [7].

FLOWer is a strongly parallel block-structured compressible Navier-Stokes CFD solver mostly written in Fortran and originally developed by the DLR (German Aerospace Center) as part of the MEGAFLOW project [5]. It can use the characteristic method [8] for its farfield BC by pre-treating the ghost cells of the constraint. An extensively modified version of FLOWer is used in this study. In the legacy version of FLOWer [9, 10], inserting turbulence was usually done by setting a constant wind profile at the inlet and then, after a buffer zone, using forcing terms in the solution of the Navier-Stokes equations. The wind direction of insertion was generally fixed, stability treatment of the insertion was limited as it did not rely on the characteristic method, and a restrictive input file and meshing strategy had to be used. As such, the inlet boundary condition and the other boundary conditions of the simulation domain had to be located far away from the terrain and the bodies being investigated to avoid uncontrolled numerical errors or divergence.

In the new implementation, the Gust BC preprocessing is performed by a separate multithreaded Python script instead of inside the Fortran/MPI code, saving CPU hours on the supercomputer. This Python script reads 3D velocity vector data which is defined for each boundary cell and each time step, thus effectively conducting time and space interpolation before running FLOWer. The velocity data is then stored in a Tecplot SZPLT file, using the cell-centered format to eliminate redundancy and the need for interpolation onto the computational mesh. Then, on the HPC (High Performance Computing) system, FLOWer reads the

¹<https://windlab.hlrs.de/dataset/flower-gust-bc-torque2026>

SZPLT file in parallel and retains the boundary values for the entire simulation. The zone-based reading of that file format allows efficient parallel loading of the velocities, so that each MPI rank reads only its attributed zones. Linear temporal interpolation is performed when the timestep of the input data does not match the simulation timestep. Furthermore, to ensure numerical stability, the Gust BC is implemented as a modification of the FLOWer farfield BC [8, 11], which is briefly described as follows: the non-reflecting farfield BC is based on a local characteristic decomposition of the compressible Euler equations, where eigenvalues indicate the propagation direction of characteristic waves normal to the boundary; depending on the eigenvalue sign, flow information is either extrapolated from the computational domain or prescribed from freestream values; and, for subsonic flow, using a smooth switching condition based on the velocity vector being enforced at the cell, only flow entering the domain is forced: when the input flow vector points outside of the domain, the pressure from the farfield is used and the velocity is taken from the flow state at the first cell inside the domain. The farfield BC uses static dimensionless values for the reference pressure and density; for air, the reference temperature could replace one of these using the ideal gas law, but in its current form the farfield BC uses constant values, and the freestream values are only used to dimensionalize the final results. Thus, in the Gust BC, the three components of the velocity are inserted into the neighboring ghost cell of each boundary cell at each subiteration within a timestep. In doing so, no information about grid coordinates is needed during the simulation to determine the correct cell values for the velocity components. Instead, these velocities are stored in arrays that correspond to the i -, j -, and k -indices of the computational grid. The other flow variables are not constrained, but rather treated as for a farfield characteristic boundary condition. This implementation provides several key improvements: the boundary condition can be used on all sides of the simulation domain or on curved faces, and the wind vector can turn as desired; imposing the Gust BC simultaneously on all boundaries does not cause instability because the velocities of flow leaving the domain are not forced; if coupling with a precursor simulation, it prevents unphysical cross-flows along the lateral edges; and the Python script reads the CGNS (CFD General Notation System) FLOWer grid in the preprocessing step and identifies the physical coordinates of each boundary cell, removing any dependency on cell index ordering. Since boundary values are precomputed, HPC processors do not idle waiting for runtime boundary calculations while still being billed per node-hour. Additionally, a user-defined flag enables the loading of only the desired velocity components, further saving resources.

3. Case Studies

Two 750 kW research wind turbines are installed at the onset of the Swabian Alps mountain range at the WINSSENT² test site and are modeled using DDES within various research projects of the group [12–14]. The test site is equipped with four 100 m meteorological masts each equipped with four ultrasonic anemometers (at 25 m, 45.5 m, 72.5 m and 96 m) to characterize the wind field as affected by the complexity of the terrain.

Because of the relevance of the WINSSENT test site to the research group and its rich availability of experimental equipment, a turbulent velocity field measured there was used to generate a turbulence box and subsequently insert it using the new Gust BC into the computational grids shown in Fig. 1. In the figure, only block boundaries are drawn, and the cell sizes are in the order of 1 m for the gray blocks and 2 m for the cyan blocks. The gray zone of the Cuboid-1m-2m (case A) grid is exactly identical to the Cuboid grid (case B), although its block topology is divided differently. Those grids were designed to verify both accuracy and numerical stability

²<https://winsent.de/> (Wind Science and Engineering Test Site in Complex Terrain)

Figure 1. CFD meshes of the case study; lines show block borders and any block face touched by a star marker is treated by the Gust BC.

under challenging numerical conditions such as the vicinity of boundaries and curved domains. Therefore, the Cylindrical (case C) presents the challenge of having curved boundary domains and non-isometric cells and the Spherical (case D) is on top of this very small, thus bringing all boundaries close to each other. Case E tests a split-grid approach: case B's domain is divided into a precursor (part 1) and a receiver (part 2) simulation. The precursor receives the same Mann box inflow as all other cases via the Gust BC. Neither simulation uses periodic boundary conditions; the precursor is therefore not a precursor in the traditional sense where turbulence is generated by the simulation itself, but rather carries the turbulence through its domain. At the interface (168 m), the precursor's last cell layer before its farfield outlet serves as input for the receiver via the Gust BC. This explores whether such decoupling could reduce computational costs while enabling domain-specific optimization. The grid cell sizes of 1 m in the turbulence tunnel and the 2:1 growth represent the current practice in the group [9, 10, 12–14].

To allow consistent comparison, the same physical space, located at and downstream of the inflow met mast, is included and meshed with the same resolution in all grids of this study. Also, a single turbulence box and atmospheric boundary layer (ABL) at moderate wind velocities was used for all previously given cases (A-E) and was generated using Hipersim [15] (Mann box [6]) box and constrained to the WINSSENT test site data coming from North-West met mast using a method adapted from [16]. The turbulence data for the test case of this paper was recorded by the Northwest Met Mast on March 10, 2021 between 11:30 and 11:35 CET. The 20 Hz signal of the three velocity components was sampled at every second entry from sonic anemometers located at heights of 25 m, 46 m, 72 m (approximate turbine hub height), and 97 m AGL (above ground level). From the collected data, a turbulence length scale $L = 55$ and an anisotropy parameter $\Gamma = 3$ were obtained through a manual fitting procedure, repeatedly generating Mann boxes and comparing their spectra graphically against those of the field measurements. They were then fed to Hipersim to return a Mann turbulence box with $U_{box} = 6.87 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ and a turbulence intensity $TI = 0.25$. The box was then processed using the `constrain_field_1d` function in Hipersim to fit the met mast signals for each of the three flow directions. The spatial distortion and turbulence scaling schemes of prior work [16] are also applied. The measured signals at each height were averaged over the 5 min recording period and fitted to a Hellmann power-law profile using least squares. The reference velocity $U(z_{ref})$ was then chosen as the constant velocity that minimizes the integrated difference (area) between the Hellmann profile and a uniform flow, and this value was adopted as U_{box} . This yielded $U(z_{ref}) \equiv U_{box} = 6.87 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, $z_{ref} = 56.3 \text{ m}$, and Hellmann exponent $\alpha = 0.377$. The slightly non-neutral characteristics of the selected measurement period are suspected to originate primarily from the complex terrain upstream of the mast (a steep hill and forest at approximately 150 m and 60 m upwind, respectively) rather than from thermal effects. The cloud cover during the measurement and many hours before

varied between 7/8 and 8/8 oktas (DWD Station Stötten auf der Schwäbischen Alb, ID 4887), strongly limiting solar-driven thermal influences. Finally, the combined average ABL profile and turbulence box yield the 3D velocity field that is mapped onto the CFD domain boundaries by the Gust BC during the simulation. All preprocessing, including the superposition of the mean profile and the turbulent fluctuations, is performed before the simulation in the Python script described in Section 2. The velocity field was fed into the inflow planes indicated by star markers in Fig. 1. Any block boundary that is adjacent to a star uses the Gust BC; the remaining boundaries are treated as characteristic variable farfield BC, except for the stress case, described later. Inserting turbulence only at the inlet avoids deformation of structures that would occur if a frozen turbulence box (Mann box) were sampled using the spatial distortion method [16] at a position that shifts along the wind direction. The stress test (case F), conducted with the Spherical grid, differs slightly from the other cases. Its inflow gradually rotates 360° about the Z-axis, followed by 90° about the Y-axis; during this rotation, the ABL profile transitions into a turbulent jet directed toward the ground. Its turbulence box has identical parameters to the other cases but is not constrained to match the measured coherent structures. The Gust BC is used on all boundaries except the ground, where both slip and farfield conditions are tested. This case is admittedly not representative of real wind conditions but was designed specifically to test the robustness of the Gust BC and FLOWer, demonstrating that turbulent flow can be seamlessly inserted from any boundary without causing divergence.

All simulations employ fifth-order WENO (Weighted Essentially Non-Oscillatory) spatial discretization, DDES turbulence modeling, and non-reflecting farfield boundary conditions. All simulations are initialized from standstill. The domain is not initialized with the Mann box velocity field so that the turbulence evolves naturally within the CFD domain from a state that is consistent with the Navier-Stokes equations. The 80 s initial delay allows the flow field to fully develop before the evaluation begins. Apart from the stress case, the test cases of this paper do not include solid walls that contribute to turbulence generation, although typical simulations of the group with complex terrain do include ground walls with no-slip conditions. The Cuboid and Cylindrical CFD meshes cover the positions of the four meteorological masts of the WINSSENT test site, plus a small buffer, and their height would allow the insertion of one of its wind turbines. The simulated domain heights differ between the meshes (Fig. 1). Since the reference turbine has a hub height of 73 m [14], the focus is on the velocity fluctuations in the Prandtl layer without an inversion layer or wind veer. A timestep of 0.0625 s is used to guarantee a Courant number $Co < 0.5$ everywhere in the DDES simulation. The timestep of the generated Mann box matches the signal sampling at 0.1 s and is linearly interpolated to match the FLOWer timestep. This timestep ensures that at least one turbulence data point passes through each cell at each timestep, though coarser temporal resolution would suffice. A spatial resolution of 0.7 m is used for the generated Mann box, although the literature [17] reports that inflow grid resolutions up to 4 times coarser than the CFD grid also yield accurate results. A coarser Mann box could therefore have been used, but since the Hipersim-based preprocessing represents a small fraction of the total computational cost, there was no incentive to reduce its resolution.

4. Results and Discussion

In this section, the results of the test cases are first inspected qualitatively and then quantitatively to verify that the inflow turbulent structures are inserted and preserved as expected into the computational domain and that boundary reflections remain minimal. To be consistent with FLOWer's internal structure and the symmetric grids, all presented results are taken at the cell

centers of the first layer of cells after the midplane in the y -direction. The inflow turbulence box (Gust BC input) is shown in Fig. 2 at the y -midplane along with the resulting FLOWer streamwise velocity field. Here, the box has a resolution of 0.7 m and FLOWer has 1.0 m.

Figure 2. Inserted turbulence (a), CFD flow field (b), and their absolute difference (c) at the midplane of case B at $t = 250$ s.

The coherent structures of the Mann box are well reproduced in the first portion of the FLOWer domain, as confirmed by the near-zero differences in Fig. 2c. Further downstream, the differences grow as the frozen turbulence adjusts to the Navier-Stokes equations, lateral velocity contributions redistribute structures, and the energy cascade transfers energy to smaller scales. To further analyze the same test case, the velocities at hub height in the y -midplane of case B are shown in Fig. 3, where τ is the convective time lag at the point of observation. Figure 3 confirms that the flow structure is very well inserted and preserved at 5 m for u and w , then degrades as expected farther downstream. Interestingly, the lateral velocity (v) components are less well inserted and lose their correlation much faster than the other two components. The limitation of the v and w fields in reproducing the coherent structures equally well as u inside the FLOWer domain may also be due to the vicinity of the non-streamwise farfield BCs. This could, however, not be confirmed by inspection of the correlation plots of case A, shown later in Fig. 4, likely due to the larger turbulent inlet of that case.

We rely on the Eulerian two-point space-time correlation (Pearson) coefficient R_{ij} , as in [2, 18, 19], and the normalized variance σ_p^{*2} , as in [20], both defined in Eq. (1), to monitor the

Figure 3. Inflow and FLOWer velocities at 3 downstream positions for case B at 72.5 m AGL.

Figure 4. Correlation of velocity fluctuations at a height of 72.5 m.

evolution of the velocity and pressure fluctuations through the domain, respectively. We also rely on the TKE (Turbulent Kinetic Energy) k to analyze the flow profile.

$$R_{ij} = \frac{\langle u'_i(x, t_0) u'_j(x + \Delta x, t_0 + \tau) \rangle}{\sqrt{\langle u'^2_i(x, t_0) \rangle \langle u'^2_j(x + \Delta x, t_0 + \tau) \rangle}} \quad \sigma_p^{*2} = \frac{\langle p'^2 \rangle}{\rho^2 U_{\text{ref}}^4} \quad k = \frac{1}{2} (\langle u'^2_x \rangle + \langle u'^2_y \rangle + \langle u'^2_z \rangle) \quad (1)$$

There, x and Δx are the streamwise inflow position and distance to the sampling point, t_0 is the time at inflow, u'_i is the velocity fluctuation in the i -direction, $\langle \cdot \rangle$ denotes the time average, ρ is the local density, and $U_{\text{ref}} = U(z_{\text{ref}}) = 6.87 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, as before. Throughout this work, $i \equiv j$, the convective time is a function of sampling height z , and τ is obtained from the velocity at the sampling point height as given by Hellman's law. For clarity, R_{xx} , R_{yy} , and R_{zz} give the correlation of u_x , u_y , u_z , which are the streamwise, lateral, and vertical velocity components also known as u , v , and w . The time averaging is done over a time window of constant size, which is chosen to be as large as the farthest sampling point in the domain allows; for the signal at 72.5 m, this permits the window of 170 s which was shown for case B in Fig. 3. Both the velocity and pressure fluctuation plots rely on the same time samples, and an initial delay of 80 s allows the CFD domain to adapt from its initial standstill.

The downstream evolution of the velocity fluctuation correlations with the Mann Box is shown in Fig. 4, where unity indicates perfect agreement between the inlet and the CFD solution at the sampling point. The preservation of the turbulence agrees with the expected behavior of atmospheric turbulence [21]. The correlation of the velocity fluctuations at the onset of the domain clearly confirms that the turbulent structures are very well inserted by the Gust BC, with the streamwise component showing near-unity correlation at 5 m. As expected, high-frequency components are smoothed out and the turbulent structures tend to dissipate downstream due to the finite mesh resolution, with correlations dropping below 0.5 after approximately 50 m. Nonetheless, as shown in Fig. 3, the larger coherent structures remain visible in the time signal up to 100 m, while at 300 m most structures have been destroyed by the energy cascade or displaced laterally.

The pressure fluctuations are shown in Fig. 5 and remain small throughout the domain, except at the boundaries, where they grow, which is expected. Leaving the inflow boundary,

Figure 5. Variance of pressure fluctuations at a height of 72.5 m.

they decrease rapidly and remain small farther into the domain, consistent with observations by [22] and [20]. Interestingly, the curved domains (cases C and D) exhibit higher initial pressure fluctuations but decay more rapidly to lower values than the cuboid cases. Those higher initial values may result from the characteristic decomposition being less accurate when cell faces are not aligned with the primary flow direction, while the faster decay suggests that curved farfield boundaries provide better acoustic radiation characteristics, allowing pressure disturbances to exit the domain more freely.

The split mesh configuration of case E compares very well with case B, yielding nearly identical correlations until the flow approaches the first outlet of case E (168 m), passes through it, and is inserted into the receiver simulation. The pressure variance of case E also shows the expected jump at the interface between the two simulations (168 m), but quickly diminishes back to values similar to those of the other cases. This confirms the feasibility of using outflow data from an upstream precursor simulation as inflow data for a subsequent receiver simulation. Thus, terrain-scale and turbine-scale modeling can be separated using a one-way FLOWer-to-FLOWer coupling. Both cases A and C show u and v correlations that decay slightly faster than those of case B. For case C, this is most likely due to the influence of the cylindrical mesh, which causes the inlet and side BCs to be closer to the point of interest and thus causes more numerical noise. For case A, the presence of a larger inlet domain where the Gust BC is applied causes turbulent interactions between the 2 m and 1 m grid zones and explains differences in correlations. Of particular interest is the correlation of v (i.e. R_{yy}), which not only decreases more quickly than those for u and w but also reaches and maintains negative correlations for a considerable portion of the domain. This negative correlation can also be seen in the v signal of Fig. 3 at 100 m downstream, which tends to show velocity fluctuations in the opposite direction to those of the inflow. Also interesting to observe from that figure is that the v signal is already damped after 5 m, although the w signal is significantly less damped at that position and the u signal accurately reproduces the inflow. The differing behaviors of v and w are not attributed to the presence of the ground, because the simulations of all cases except F used a farfield BC on all non-inlet planes, but may be related to the specific Mann box used here. Another indication of this is that the negative correlation does not occur for the signal at a height of 25 m.

Figure 6 shows the correlation and pressure plots at a signal height of 25 m for cases B and D, along with a rendering of the stress case F with slip ground. As seen by the maximum velocities incurred, the stress test also remained stable, with velocities inserted into the domain matching expectations. The video of this rendering is available online³, showing both ground boundary treatments (farfield and slip). The video illustrates the elevated velocities produced by the rotating turbulent jet descending from above, as well as flow insertion at non-negligible velocities near the intersection of the side and ground boundaries. Throughout these challenging conditions, the FLOWer simulation converges cleanly, as evidenced by the maximum velocity

³<https://youtu.be/8w09bbNeKRg>

Figure 6. Correlation of velocity fluctuations and variance of pressure fluctuations at a height of 25 m for cases B and D along with rendering of the stress test (case F) at time 199.9 s.

Figure 7. Mean velocity (top) and TKE (bottom) profiles following a flow section into the domain.

remaining bounded.

The mean velocity and TKE profiles along the domain are shown in Fig. 7, sampled using the same flow section and time range as for the time signals, correlations, and pressure fluctuations. In the figure, the Mann Box profiles remain constant because they represent frozen turbulence observing the same flow section. The mean velocity is nearly perfectly inserted for all cases and evolves due to the previously discussed phenomena. The influence of the approaching outlet boundary condition is clearly visible in all cases except for case A, which benefits from an outlet buffer zone with 2 m edge-length cells that extends >100 m beyond the other domains, thereby better preserving the mean velocity profile shape. The outlet BC of case E at 168 m also visibly affects the mean velocity, suggesting that for applied cases the precursor domain should extend slightly beyond the receiver’s insertion point. All cases exhibit a slight reduction of TKE upon entering the domain, as FLOWer adjusts the Mann box to its Navier-Stokes equations and smooths non-normal flow components at the inlet. Case A shows better overall TKE preservation, while the cylindrical mesh of case C shows the most fluctuating TKE profile, which may be explained by the curved inlet allowing lateral velocity components to enter the domain more freely. These additional lateral contributions may also explain the apparent increase of TKE observed for case C. A clear impact of the outlet BC of case E at 168 m on the TKE is

difficult to identify.

Overall, the results demonstrate that the Gust BC successfully inserts turbulent structures into the computational domain, where they evolve as expected given the properties of DDES and the energy cascade, without unwanted reflections.

5. Conclusion

In this work, an improved gust boundary condition incorporating the characteristic method and supporting multiple inflow planes has been presented and validated with the turbulent inflow of a complex terrain site. Unlike the legacy approach that required buffer zones and careful handling of lateral boundaries to avoid pressure oscillations and diverging velocities, the new Gust BC remains stable even under strongly varying wind directions inserted on every boundary of the domain. Quantitative assessment through two-point (Pearson) correlation coefficients demonstrated that turbulent structures inserted at the inlet are transported and preserved as physically expected for all tested configurations. Correlations for u and w start near unity and decay gradually downstream, with the largest coherent structures well preserved far into the domain. At the height of 72.5 m, the lateral velocity component (v) shows faster decorrelation, reaching negative values in some cases, which appears related to the specific turbulence box rather than boundary effects. The split-domain approach shows promise for decoupled simulations, with correlations nearly identical to the single-domain case and a pressure variance that quickly returns to a value as low as without the interface. Multi-resolution and curved meshes (cases A and C) exhibit slightly faster correlation decay, attributable to proximity of boundaries, lateral inflow, or a larger turbulent inflow zone. The pressure fluctuations remain at acceptable levels throughout the domain, only increasing near boundaries as expected. The mean velocity and TKE profiles displayed the expected behavior of being nearly perfectly inserted and then gradually evolving before being influenced by the approaching outlet BC. The Gust BC method presented in this paper thus offers a robust and efficient way to insert turbulence from and into a complex terrain, enhancing the accuracy and stability of CFD simulations for wind turbine applications. Future work will address thermal stratification effects for atmospheric boundary layer applications.

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